

Development of smart 2nd fertilizer application system by using canopy sensor

Eiji Morimoto¹, Hiromi Fuji¹, Tsuyoshi Yoshida², Shinkai Shu², Norihiro Kamijima³, Yoshiaki Hasegawa⁴

¹ Faculty of Agriculture, Tottori University

² Topcon Co.Ltd.

³ Iseki Co.Ltd.

⁴ Hatsuta Industrial Co. Ltd.

Abstract

This research developed Smart 2nd Fertilizer Application System (SFAS) using canopy sensor to equalize growth of rice paddy and prevention from lodging upon harvest. The CropSpec™ was applied as a canopy sensor for measuring N status in order to operate variable application. The amount of fertilizer applied was determined by using measured value (S1) and producer's experience. The SFAS recorded geo-referenced information in order to apply for site-specific crop management exercises for creating a prescription map for other and future operations, as well as to provide an "as applied" application record for the grower. The result of field experiment, the correlation between N status and S1 was $R^2=0.57$. The maximum value of S1 was 36.4, the minimum was 25.0 and the average was 30.7, respectively. This application system could reduce the amount of fertilizer among the rich N zone. As a result, the system could save 20% of fertilizer than conventional way. Result of crop yield sampling analysis, lodging spot produced 850kg/10a of rough rice, while brown rice was 600kg/10a. No-lodging spot produced rough and brown rice were 700kg/10a and 560kg/10a, respectively. No-lodging data indicated that the ratio of rough rice and brown rice weight (commercialization rate) was 9% higher than that of lodging spot data. In this presentation, we discussed how the variable rate application could contribute to prevent lodging and improve rice quality.

Introduction

In Japan, rice is an important and indispensable crop. But the number of rice farmer decreased by 34% in 2005 from 20 years to 2015. Along with that, the area of paddy field managed by one farmer has expanded, and work burden is increasing (Yagi, H. 2016). Some large scale corporate farming organizations manage 300-500 fields. In addition, spatiotemporal variation of soil is expanding in extensive fields especially in the field that executed the land readjustments. In such field, there is a problem of lodging. Lodging is a common problem in rice cultivar. Lodging can reduce yield, quality of production, and mechanical harvesting efficiency (Setter, T.L. 1997). To prevent lodging, it necessary to produce uniform plants height. In previous research, it was found that application of N fertilizers increased the plant height significantly (Chaturvedi, I. 2005). Based on this finding, it is safe to presume that variable rate fertilizer application may offer the effective method to make the plant grow evenly. The variable rate fertilizer application is also important in terms of reduction of fertilizer and sustainable farm management. By doing site-specific nutrient management, yield increases can be achieved in correlation with a decrease in the average N application. Compared to the current farmers' practices, site-specific nutrient management reduced N losses from fertilizer by 30–40% and promote profitability by additional 12% total average net return (Dobermann, A. *et al.*, 2002).

Based on those situation, in this study we developed SFAS. SFAS is a real-time variable rate fertilizer application system, based on leaf N sensor. Previous studies have suggested that it is possible to measure crop N status with optical instruments. Since most leaf nitrogen is contained in chlorophyll molecules, there is a strong relationship between leaf nitrogen and leaf chlorophyll content (Erdle, K. *et al.*, 2011). Other research in rice cultivation indicated that active crop canopy sensor (GreenSeeker, trimble) could be used to estimate yield potential and responsiveness to additional topdressing N application at stem elongation or booting stage, but the performance was less satisfactory at higher yielding site (Yao, Y. *et al.*, 2012). Therefore, in this study we alternative active sensor (CropSpec, Topcon) to estimate the N status. In addition, we made the map of crop N status to use for farm management. And we verify the verification of usability of real-time variable-rate fertilizer-application.

Materials and method

1. Optical sensor

To estimate crop N status, we use CropSpec (Topcon) on-the-go canopy sensor (Fig.1). CropSpec is an active sensor with operational wavebands of 730-740nm and 800-810nm, the device dimensions are 200×80×80mm, with viewing angle of 36°. With technology based on Topcon's core competency of optics, CropSpec uses pulsing laser diodes for sensing. The sensor measures plant reflectance to determine chlorophyll content, which is closely related to the nitrogen concentration in the leaf. The sensors mounted on the right and left side of the high-clearance tractor, and the mounting height is set at 2985mm (Fig.2, Fig.3). In this research, the observation results from CropSpec is noted as S1.

Figure1. Picture of CropSpec

2. High-clearance tractor and applicator

The high-clearance tractor (JKB23, Iseki) was applied for base platform (Fig. 2). The specification of the platform is as follows: length: 4130mm, width: 1975mm and height: 2475mm. Fertilizer applied based on the crop N status monitoring data with the boom tabula. Boom tabula fitted behind at right and left side of the JKB23. That distance from CropSpec is 2917mm and from ground is 1004mm. The right and left application width were 15m respectively. To make the crop N status map we recorded the location of fertilized place every second with DGPS (Differential GPS). The DGPS is mounted on the front of the high-clearance tractor. The distance from boom tabula is 3062mm, 1768mm above the ground (Fig. 3).

Figure 2. JKB23 (Iseki)

Figure 3. Positional relation of CropSpec, Boom tabula and DGPS on JKB23.

3. Variable rate fertilizer application

Variable rate fertilizer application is placed separately on the right and left of the boom-tabula. The amount of N fertilizer calculated from right and left S1 by console. The limitation of large and small amount of fertilizer were decided according to the minimum and maximum S1 value. We used teaching method to observe the maximum and minimum S1. To do teaching, JKB23 drove through the field while sensing by each side CropSpec without fertilizer application. After teaching, the tractor drove through the field while variable rate application system work based on real-time observation value from each side of the CropSpec. Right and left observation position and S1 were recorded every second while observing of CropSpec automatically using data-logger.

4. Experimental field and date

The experiment conducted in Takemoto farm (36°25'44.9"N 136°30'03.0"E). And the experiment field is 10ha. We use the rice cultivar "Koshihikari" in this experiment. Observation with canopy sensor carried out in July 2016. Sampling was carried out in 13 fields in the experimental fields. And we sampled about 5 rice plants in high S1 point and low S1 point each of the 13 field. The two points are given points which selected by screening of the S1 status map. Subsequently we measured N content of the samples to compare measured and S1 value.

Result and Discussion

1. The analysis of crop N status

From the result and analysis of sampling plants, we confirmed that S1 is correlated the actual N status of rice plants. The average of N content in all high S1 points and low S1 points were 1.67 % and 1.31 % respectively. The difference of N content between the average of high S1 points and low S1 points is 0.36%.

2. S1 and N input map

S1 and N input map based on the sensing data from CropSpec and DGPS made by FARMS (Fig.4). Left map shows S1 and right map shows N input prescription in same area where the JKB23 drove. Comparing left and right map, the area which have high S1 value had low N input. On the contrary, the area which have low value of S1 had high N input. The two map suggest that N input well reflect S1 value. From the above result, it is found that SFAS succeeded in the variable rate 2nd fertilizer application in real time.

Figure 4. Left map is S1 status determined from CropSpec hyperspectral image and right map is N input prescription image calculated from S1 of 2nd fertilizer application, July 8-9, 2016, for rice field at Takemoto farm. N input content units are kg/10a.

3. Decision of N fertilizer level

N fertilizer level decided using maximum and minimum S1 value obtained by teaching and the standard N fertilizer level. According to the teaching, maximum and minimum S1 value were 36.4 and 25.0 respectively and the standard amount of N was 3.0kg/10a in this time. Consequently, the highest and lowest amount of N were decided by 2.5kg/10a and 3.5kg/10a at S1 value 36.4 and 25.0. All amount of N is calculated from the graph of Fig. 5 made by using those data. The amount of N not become lower and higher than 2.5 and 3.5kg/10a even if S1 become above 3.5 or under 2.5.

Figure 5. Relationship between the amount of N and S1. The amount of N varying from 2.5 to 3.5 kg/10a and it unchanging even if S1 above 36.4 or under 25.0.

4. Right and left S1 histogram

Histogram of S1 which the data observation from right and left CropSpec when variable rate application in 7/7-11 is Figure.6. S1 of right side CropSpec is higher than that of left side by and large. According to the histogram it is better to do right and left independent variable rate fertilizer application not to take right and left S1 average.

Figure 6. Histogram of S1. Red bar is S1 distribution of right side and blue bar is S1 distribution of left side. Number of measurement points was 24852.

Conclusion

In this study, we succeed in real-time variable rate 2nd fertilizer application based on S1 value and standard N fertilizer level assessed by producer. And it proved that it is necessary for correct fertilizer application to do right and left boom tabula independent variable rate fertilizer application. The observation value from CropSpec strung to the information on the location from DGPS can be important data for farm management. The S1 status map help producer to grasp fields crop N status. In addition, SFAS with S1 status can make the crops growth equalize so that, it can prevent lodging. In future, producer can probably make next year's schedule for fertilizer application by using accumulated data over the years.

Acknowledgements

This project was supported by Council for Science, Technology and Innovation (CSTI), Cross-ministerial Strategic Innovation Promotion Program (SIP), 'Technologies for creating next-generation agriculture, forestry and fisheries' (funding agency: Bio-oriented Technology Research Advancement Institution).

Reference

- Chaturvedi I 2005. Effect of nitrogen fertilizers on growth, yield and quality of hybridrice (*Oryza Sativa*). Central European Agriculture 6: 611–618.
- Doberman A, Witt C, Dawe D, Abdulrachman S, Gines HC, Nagarajan R, Satawathananont S, Son TT, Tan PS, Wang GH, Chien NV, Thoa VTK, Phung CV, Stalin P, Muthukrishnan P, Ravi V, Babu M, Chatupom S, Sookthongsa J, Sun Q, Fu R, Simbahan GC, Adviento MAA 2002. Site-specific nutrient management for intensive rice cropping system in Asia. Field Crop Research 74: 37–66.
- Erdle K, Mistele B, Schmidhalter U 2011. Comparison of active and passive spectral sensors in discriminating biomass parameters and nitrogen status in wheat cultivars. Field Crop Research 124: 74–84.
- Setter TL, Laureles EV, Mazaredo AM 1997. Lodging reduces yield of rice by self-shading and reductions in canopy photosynthesis. Field Crop Research 49: 95–106.
- Yagi H 2016. Transformation in Japan Paddy farming and increasing large-scale management. Research report of Japan Agricultural Research Institute: Agricultural Research 29: 65–94.
- Yao Y, Miao Y, Huang S, Gao L, Ma X, Zhao G, Jiang R, Chen X, Zhang F, Yu K, Gnyp LG, Bareth G, Liu C, Zhao L, Yang W, Zhu H 2012. Active canopy sensor-based precision N management strategy for rice. Agronomy for Sustainable Development 32: 925–933.